

Viscosity of Solid-liquid Mixtures

R. P. Bhatnagar* and S. H. Mishal

The viscosity equation,

$$(\eta_m)^{\frac{1}{3}} = \frac{d(x_1R_1 + x_2R_2 + \dots + x_nR_n)}{M_m},$$

suggested by Shukla and Bhatnagar¹ was tested by them for binary and ternary² liquid—liquid mixtures. The equation was derived from the equation of Smyth *et al*³. for computing the viscosity (in millipoises) of a liquid—liquid mixture of 'n' components from values of the rheochors (*R*) and mole fractions (*x*₁ and *x*₂) of the components and also density (*d*) and mean molecular weight of the mixture (*M*_m).

In the present work this equation has been tested for solid—liquid mixtures. The calculated results have been compared with the observed viscosity by Subnis and Bhagwat⁴. Our results are recorded in Tables I and II.

The equation of Shukla and Bhatnagar¹, which has been tested for solid—liquid mixtures in the present work, yielded a general maximum error of 10%. In comparison with a maximum error of 4% for liquid—liquid mixture, shown by these workers, a limit of 10% for solid—liquid mixture is quite reasonable. The viscosity equations of Smyth *et al*³. and Katz *et al*⁵. were mainly used for liquid—liquid systems and their applicability with such additive constitutive properties as molar polarisation and surface tension was a sound one. As the equation of Shukla and Bhatnagar is based on similar concepts, its applicability to liquid—liquid systems is but expected. But the present studies have made it clear that it is also applicable to solid—liquid mixtures with a reasonable limit of general error. Lima⁶, using Sauder's viscosity constant, also proposed a viscosity equation on the basis of the equation of Smyth *et al*³. But Lima's equation even for liquid-liquid systems gave as high limits of % error as 15 (for butyl alcohol and benzene). Shukla and Bhatnagar's equation thus appears to be better in comparison with Lima's for computing viscosity of solid—liquid mixtures, both binary and ternary, with reasonable accuracy.

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, Government Science College, Gwalior, M.P.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1955, **59**, 988.
2. *Ibid.*, 1956, **60**, 809.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **52**, 1736.
4. *This Journal*, 1951, **28**, 275.
5. Katz *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1943, **35**, 239, 1091.
6. Lima, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 1052.

TABLE I.

Solid—liquid binary mixture.

x_1	x_2	d	R	M_m	$\eta \times 10^3$		%Error.
					Calc	Obs.	
Urea—water.							
0.0436	0.9514	1.040	60.90	20.02	9.5819	8.72	9.96
0.0094	0.9906	1.070	63.77	22.18	10.469	9.91	5.63
0.1318	0.8682	1.096	65.20	23.54	11.658	10.87	7.25
Acetamide—water.							
0.0438	0.9562	1.009	86.00	19.80	10.902	10.15	7.48
0.0701	0.9299	1.016	86.98	21.25	12.680	11.76	7.64
0.1282	0.8718	1.023	87.50	23.07	14.977	14.16	5.76
Chloral hydrate—water.							
0.0260	0.9740	1.089	172.20	21.84	13.817	12.70	6.28
0.0441	0.9559	1.158	171.60	24.50	17.451	16.31	6.97
0.0600	0.9400	1.200	169.90	26.87	19.989	18.41	6.84

TABLE II

Solid—liquid ternary mixtures.

x_1	x_2	x_3	d	M_m	$\eta \times 10^3$		%Error.
					Calc.	Obs.	
Acetamide—Urea—water.							
0.0258	0.0910	0.8832	1.034	22.81	13.440	12.95	4.96
0.0858	0.0862	0.8280	1.070	25.14	13.713	14.17	3.53
0.1174	0.0324	0.8502	1.087	24.27	11.912	12.62	7.68
Acetamide—chloral hydrate—water.							
0.3979	0.0253	0.8766	1.100	25.79	18.222	16.76	8.73
0.0599	0.0428	0.9813	1.147	26.77	19.469	18.62	7.55
0.1593	0.0119	0.8288	1.070	26.29	19.383	16.55	9.35
Chloral hydrate—acetylurea—water.							
0.9494	0.0468	0.9038	1.183	27.27	17.253	17.31	0.23
0.0343	0.0862	0.8795	1.171	26.68	14.224	15.72	6.96
0.0286	0.0983	0.8731	1.162	26.34	13.368	15.65	16.65

Rheochors used in calculations: water 23.73; urea 63.29; acetamide 87.16; chloral hydrate 171.22; acetyl urea 58.404).

Thanks of the authors are due to Dr. R. P. Shukla, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Chhatarpur, M. P., for his keen interest in the work.